

BARRIERS AND SOLUTIONS TO THE FORMATION OF VILLAGE STUNTING REDUCTION ACCELERATION TEAMS (TPPS) IN BATUI SELATAN SUB-DISTRICT, BANGGAI DISTRICT

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Abstract

Background: Village-level Stunting Reduction Acceleration Teams (TPPS) play an important role in reducing stunting in Indonesia. However, the existence of TPPS in villages has not been widely recognized. This study aims to explore the barriers and solutions to establishing TPPS in villages. **Methods:** The study was conducted for 3 months in Ombolu, Sinorang and Bonebalantak villages in Batui Selatan sub-district. The research location was chosen with consideration of the prevalence of nutritional status, geographical location and ethnicity. This study was a qualitative study with 15 informants. Data related to the existence of the TPPS and barriers to the establishment of village TPPS were obtained through *in-depth* interviews. Qualitative data were processed by searching for keywords and then content analysis was conducted. Qualitative data analysis uses an inductive thinking process. **Results:** The results showed that the majority of informants had heard of the term TPPS. However, all informants stated that the TPPS had not yet been formed. There are various obstacles in forming the village TPPS, including: the village government's perception that there is already a team formed, the opinion that every time a team is formed, it is always accompanied by honorarium/incentives, including limited human resources and no technical socialization in forming the TPPS. The solution to overcome the obstacles was to provide knowledge and understanding to village stakeholders through persuasive and informative approaches. **Conclusion:** The village TPPS is difficult to form because there has been no socialization, the perception that there is already a team formed, limited funds and human resources. The solution is to take a persuasive and informative approach to the village government.

Keywords: Stunting Reduction Acceleration Team (TPPS), Stunting.

INTRODUCTION

Stunting has become a global problem today¹. The WHO report states that cases of stunting in the world in 2022 are still quite high, namely 154.3 million children². Likewise with Indonesia, the prevalence is still quite high, although there is a downward trend in the last 5 (five) years. In 2018 the prevalence was 30.8%, decreasing in 2019, 2021 and 2022 to 27.7%, 24.4% and 21.6% respectively^{3,4,5}. Similarly, in Central Sulawesi Province, in 2018, the prevalence of stunting was 32.3% and tended to decrease to 31.3% in 2019 and 29.7% in 2021 and 28.2% in 2022^{3,4,5}. Banggai District is the same, in 2019, the stunting prevalence was 29.96%, decreasing to 26% and 24.3% in 2021 and 2022 respectively^{3,4,5}. These facts show that the prevalence of stunting nationally and regionally is still higher than that targeted by WHO, RPJMN and the Ministry of Health's Strategic Plan, which is below 20%^{6,7}. In Batui Selatan sub-district, the prevalence of stunting was 8.45%, underweight 15.63%, and wasting 3.64%, but the proportion of toddlers measured only reached 78.22%, meaning that there are still toddlers whose nutritional status is unknown⁸.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has been working to reduce the number of stunted children under five by 40% by 2025¹⁷. The same thing is also done by the Indonesian government which targets to reduce stunting to 14% by 2024⁷. To achieve

this target and as a prevention effort, the Indonesian government joined the Global Scaling Up Nutrition (SUN) to strengthen its commitment to improving nutrition, also launched a national strategy (StraNas) to accelerate the reduction and prevention of stunting, and launched specific and sensitive nutrition intervention programs¹⁸. A concrete step taken by the government is the issuance of Presidential Regulation Number 72 of 2021 concerning the Acceleration of Stunting Reduction. In order to accelerate the reduction of stunting, a National Strategy for Accelerating Stunting Reduction was established by developing a national action plan through a family approach at risk of stunting. In the context of organizing the Acceleration of Stunting Reduction, a Stunting Reduction Acceleration Team (TPPS) was formed at the central level, provincial TPPS, city district TPPS, village / kelurahan level TPPS¹⁹.

Of the many levels of TPPS according to BKKBN Regulation Number 12 of 2021, the TPPS at the urban village level is the frontline in the context of efforts to accelerate stunting reduction²⁰. According to the 2022 stunting reduction progress report and 2023 action plan by BKKBN, it is stated that TPPS has been formed 99.99% throughout Indonesia²¹. However, based on our observations in the field, village governments have not been able to show the village TPPS decree and tend not to recognize the term. The village government only recognizes the Family Assistance Team (TPK) and Human Development Cadres (KPM) related to efforts to accelerate stunting reduction in the village. Thus, it is suspected that the stunting reduction acceleration program has not been well coordinated.

There is no research that examines barriers to the establishment of the TPPS. Many studies have examined the convergent action of sensitive and specific interventions. A study conducted in Banggai District showed that convergent action (integration of sensitive and specific interventions) implemented by the local government for 1 year succeeded in reducing the prevalence of stunting among children under five by 2.18% and the highest reduction (8.6%) in children under 1 year¹⁹. This study aims to determine the barriers and solutions to the establishment of village TPPS in Batui Selatan Sub-district, Banggai Regency.

METHODS

1. Location and time of research

This research was conducted in 3 villages in Batui Selatan sub-district. Kecamatan Batui Selatan is one of 23 kecamatan in Banggai district. The sub-district, which has 10 villages with an area of 327.97 km² and a population of 14,663, was expanded from Batui sub-district in 2010. The sub-district is inhabited by 11 ethnic groups, three of which are the largest: Ta'a, Bugis and Javanese.

Meanwhile, 3 villages were selected as research locations, namely Ombolu Village, Sinorang Village and Bonebalantak Village, which were considered representative of the 10 villages in Batui Selatan Sub-district. Ombolu village was expanded from Sukamaju village on June 24, 2007 with an area of 6,896 km² and is located about 12 km from the coastline. The population is around 1,515 people, dominated by Javanese, in addition to Sundanese, Balinese and Lombok as transmigrants in 1983 and 1984. The majority of the population work as farmers. Sinorang village is an old village with an area of ± 12,236 km² and a population of 2,569 people. The Ta'a tribe is the majority tribe in this village. There is one hamlet inhabited by the majority of the population located close to the beach. The majority of the population work as farmers

and some as fishermen. Bonebalantak Village was established in 1999 as an expansion of Sinorang Village, located about 3 km from the coast. The village area is 1,699 km² with a population of 2,148 people. The Bugis tribe is the majority tribe that inhabits this village. The majority of the population work as farmers. The research was conducted for 3 (three) months from November 2023 to January 2024.

2. Research design

This research uses a qualitative research framework. Where information is obtained through respondents as subjects who can pour out their own answers and feelings to get a holistic overview of the barriers and solutions to the formation of the village TPPS.

3. Informant

There were 15 informants in this study. The informants were selected from 3 villages that were considered to have sufficient knowledge of the TPPS information in their respective villages. They consisted of the village head, village secretary, head of the family welfare empowerment (PKK,) human development cadre/stunting cadre and head of the family assistance team/village midwife. The characteristics of the informants in this study can be explained in the following table.

Table 1: Informant Characteristics

No.	Name Initials	Age (Thn)	Gender	Education	Jobs
1.	WH	58	Male	HIGH SCHOOL	Head of Ombolu Village
2.	WG	52	Female	SMP	Chairperson of Ombolu Village PKK Team
3.	SN	47	Female	SARJANA	Ombolu Village Secretary
4.	ME	45	Female	SARJANA	Ombolu Village TPK Coordinator
5.	KA	31	Female	HIGH SCHOOL	KPM Ombolu Village
6.	MR	61	Male	MASTER	Sinorang Village Head
7.	NR	60	Female	SARJANA	Chairperson of Ombolu Sinorang Village PKK Team
8.	RS	51	Female	HIGH SCHOOL	Sinorang Village Secretary
9.	NI	23	Female	DIPLOMA IV	Sinorang Village TPK Coordinator
10.	ER	24	Female	DIPLOMA III	KPM Sinorang Village
11.	DW	50	Male	SARJANA	Bonebalantak Village Head
12.	KS	39	Female	SD	Chairperson of the PKK Movement Team of Bonebalantak Village
13.	AR	48	Male	HIGH SCHOOL	Bonebalantak Village Secretary
14.	RO	40	Female	SARJANA	Bonebalantak Village TPK Coordinator
15.	SM	33	Female	HIGH SCHOOL	KPM Bonebalantak Village

4. Data collection

Secondary data in the form of an overview of the research location such as: geographical and demographic location was obtained through a review of Batui Selatan sub-district government documents. Primary data related to informant characteristics, the existence of the TPPS and barriers to the establishment of the village TPPS were obtained through *in-depth* interviews with informants. In-depth

individual interviews were chosen as they represent the most widely used data collection method in qualitative research²². In-depth individual interviews allow a researcher to explore a phenomenon from an individualistic point of view²³. In addition, it is often said that in-depth individual interviews tend to reveal more detailed information than other methods²⁴.

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants individually before commencing data collection. Interviews were conducted at a time and place of the participant's choosing, namely at the village office, including at the participant's home. Field notes were taken while conducting interviews and all interviews were audio-recorded.

5. Conducting research

The research began with field observations. Next, informants were selected for in-depth interviews.

6. Data processing and analysis

Qualitative data processing obtained through in-depth interviews is carried out by studying all the data collected and selecting questions and notes that enter the interview process, looking for the meaning contained in the informant's answers so that keywords are obtained, then content analysis is carried out, then interpreted and presented in narrative form. Qualitative data analysis is carried out using an inductive thinking process. Data analysis steps through data reduction, data presentation, conclusion drawing.

RESULTS

1. Existence of TPPS

The results show that the TPPS has not yet been formed in Ombolu, Sinorang and Bonebalantak Villages. However, they have heard about the term TPPS because someone mentioned it to them. They have not yet followed up on it because they do not know whether the TPPS will only be formed at the kabupaten and kecamatan levels or will also be formed at the village level. However, they understand that this team can help reduce the prevalence of stunting. This is as stated by the following informant.

"...I've only heard about it, if I think the team was formed to help accelerate the reduction of stunting. I'm curious too, I don't know how the team is, whether it has to be formed by the village or from the kecamatan or kabupaten level..." (SN, 47 years old)

2. Obstacles and solutions to the establishment of the village TPPS

The results of interviews with informants showed that all villages used as research locations had not yet formed a TPPS. As a follow-up to these results, researchers made efforts to form the TPPS together with the village government, in this case the Village Head and Village Secretary. However, there were obstacles along the way. The results of the interviews can be described as follows:

- The village government has never received technical socialization related to the formation of the TPPS from any party, either from the sub-district government or PLKB... this is the statement:

"...we have not made this because no one has ever socialized how to make it. If this researcher wants to tell us how to make this, insha allah we will..." (AR, 47 years old)

- The village government feels that the teams formed in the village to accelerate stunting reduction have been sufficient, such as: the activity implementation team (TPK), the Human Development Cadre (KPM) and the Family Assistance Team (TPK), the cadre team:

"...here we also have a team for stunting, there are village officials, there are also cadres..posyandu cadres, stunting cadres, there are also midwives. They have done their part to reduce stunting, such as giving PMT, vitamins, milk, including posyandu. Maybe it is the same as the team that will be formed, it is also the same to reduce stunting..." (WH 58 years old)

- The formation of teams in villages is generally always accompanied by the provision of incentives or honorariums, as stated above:

"...if the village has to create this TPPS, where will their honorarium be taken from, the use of village funds has no post for TPPS honorarium. Moreover, there are already honorariums for cadres, there are already a lot of funds there. The community now knows that if they are included in the SK, they will get an honorarium..." (DW 50 years old)

- Team building requires human resources. Meanwhile, finding people to work in the health sector has always been difficult. This is what he said:

"...if you form this, who else will want it. Cadres, midwives already have their own work, they will have more work. If you want to find new people, they don't necessarily want to, they will ask about the honorarium..." (RS 51 years old)

In order to overcome the obstacles arising from the establishment of the village TPPS, the researchers approached the village stakeholders by providing explanations and understanding, as follows:

- The first obstacle was the absence of technical socialization of TPPS formation from other parties. Here, it is explained that researchers are ready to provide socialization and will assist in the formation of the TPPS in the village. With this explanation, the government
- The second obstacle is related to the perception that the village feels that it has already formed an implementer of stunting reduction activities, so there is no need to form a new team . Here I explain that this is a positive thing that needs to be appreciated. However, in addition to its task of coordinating, synergizing and evaluating the implementation of efforts to accelerate stunting reduction in the village, TPPS also contains a national action plan matrix, one of which contains targets that must be achieved and this can be known without having to wait for data information from other parties. For example, the target coverage of catinine who have a health check 3 months before marriage is 100%. The TPPS must then collect and process catin data to ensure that the target is achieved. If the target is not achieved, an evaluation will be conducted as soon as possible to take corrective or improvement actions. In addition, if so far the head of the PKK driving team, the village secretary does not seem to have the authority to accelerate efforts to reduce stunting, then through TPPS this authority is given.

- Regarding the third obstacle related to the availability of funds for honorarium/incentives for TPPS members . Here I suggest that the principle of TPPS membership is voluntary. This is the same as the recruitment of posyandu cadres at the beginning of its formation.
- Regarding the fourth obstacle, namely the limited human resources to become TPPS members . Here I explain that if you look at the composition of the TPPS membership, there are only a few new people to be recruited. This is because the director of the TPPS is the village head, the chairperson is the head of the PKK mobilizing team, the vice chairperson is the village secretary, the secretary is a family planning cadre, the two coordinators are midwives/other personnel and the KPM and TPK. So the new people who will be recruited are only to fill the positions of members in the field of the family assistance team and the field of data management. Regarding the accumulation of work, I explained that this work had already been done or was being done. Especially in relation to data related to targets such as in the RAN PASTI matrix.

Before the TPPS was formed, it was agreed to hold a meeting first. The meeting was attended by village government, BPD, KPM, TPK and posyandu cadres. During the meeting, several things were agreed upon, namely: TPPS members will not receive incentives/honors in carrying out their duties, TPPS membership is voluntary for the sake of mutual progress, TPPS members are selected from those who have been receiving incentives/honors from the APBDes for their positions/jobs in the village, and after the issuance of the decree, researchers are expected to remain with the established village TPPS in order to provide information related to the TPPS' duties and functions.

Based on this agreement, the TPPS in Ombolu Village, Sinorang Village and Bonebalantak Village were formed on November 10, November 16 and December 7, 2023, respectively. The Ombolu Village TPPS consisted of 16 members, whose ages ranged from 26-35 years old, most of whom were women and generally had a senior high school education. Meanwhile, the TPPS of Sinorang Village consists of 24 people, the majority of whom are 46-55 years old, mostly women with a high school education and generally work as housewives. Bonebalantak Village TPPS consisted of 18 people. Most of the members are 36-45 years old, mostly women, with most of them having a senior high school education, and most of them are farmers.

DISCUSSION

TPPS is an organization for the Acceleration of Stunting Reduction that is tasked with coordinating, synergizing and evaluating the Implementation of the Acceleration of Stunting Reduction. TPPS is formed at various levels, namely TPPS at the central level, TPPS at the provincial level, TPPS at the district level, TPPS at the sub-district level and TPPS at the village/kelurahan level. The results showed that the village TPPS had not yet been formed in Ombolu, Sinorang and Bonebalantak villages. However, the term TPPS has been heard because someone conveyed it. Some heard about it during meetings at the bupati and kecamatan offices, as expressed by the village heads and village secretaries. Others heard it during training, as expressed by KPM and TPK. They understand that the TPPS can help reduce the prevalence of stunting because of the cooperation between KPM, TPK and village officials.

The results of the study show that there are various obstacles that cause the TPPS to not be formed in the village. The most fundamental obstacle is the absence of technical socialization related to the establishment of the TPPS from the authorities, both from the kecamatan and BKKBN. The evidence is that they are unaware of Presidential Regulation No. 72 of 2021 and BKKBN Regulation No. 12 of 2021 as the basis for the establishment of the TPPS. Another evidence is as expressed in the second obstacle to the formation of the TPPS, namely that the village government feels that it has formed a team in the effort to accelerate stunting reduction so far. The team in question is the activity implementation team, in this case village officials, KPM, TPK and posyandu cadres. They also feel that they have done their part to reduce stunting, such as providing PMT, vitamins, milk, and weighing. They consider that the existing team is sufficient and there is no need to form a new team such as TPPS. They think that the existing team is the same as TPPS. In fact, there are differences between the teams they refer to and TPPS.

That is why socialization is important, so that there is communication between stakeholders at different levels. It is not known for certain that the socialization of the TPPS formation has not been carried out. Considering that the regulation has been issued a long time ago. The possibility is that the authorities do not understand the importance of the TPPS formation in the village, so they do not see the urgency to conduct socialization. The absence of socialization will certainly hamper the process of implementing policies to accelerate stunting reduction, one of which is the formation of the TPPS. This is in accordance with research by Milwan, et al (2023) 2023 that one of the factors influencing the implementation of policies to accelerate stunting reduction in Indonesia is the communication factor, program socialization and coordination between actors/stakeholders implementing the policy have not been fully implemented properly²⁵.

The research also found that every time a village team was formed, it was always accompanied by the provision of honorarium/incentives. Limited village finances made villages reluctant to form TPPS. It is not that they do not want to provide honorariums, but village finances are not sufficient to fund TPPS honorariums. According to them, village finances are already drained enough to pay the KPM and posyandu cadres. On the other hand, every honorarium must follow the technical guidelines for the use of village funds set by the government. Limited funds can certainly hamper efforts to accelerate stunting reduction. As stated by Indra (2023) that in the context of governance in handling stunting, one of the problems is the lack of budget funds²⁶. Similarly, Syafrawati et al (2023) revealed that an important factor in order to support the acceleration of stunting reduction is to provide adequate funding support²⁷. The same thing was revealed by Siregar (2024) that the factor that hinders the reduction in stunting prevalence rates is limited funding.²⁸

Another obstacle obtained from the results of this study is the limited human resources in the village, especially those engaged in the health sector. The village government stated that if new people were used, there would have to be funds available for their honorarium. However, when using village officials, TPK, KPM and posyandu cadres, they feel that their workload increases. Finding qualified village personnel with specific skills is not easy. Constraints in education level and exposure to information become obstacles in recruiting them as TPPS members. As stated by Milwan, et al (2023) that one of the factors affecting the implementation of policies to accelerate stunting reduction in Indonesia is the resource factor, namely the availability of human

resources in terms of quantity and quality for the implementation of stunting reduction policies in Indonesia is inadequate²⁵ .(Milwan and Sunarya, 2023)

In order to overcome the obstacles that arose related to the establishment of the village TPPS, the researchers took a persuasive and informative approach. This persuasive approach aims to convince or persuade others to accept a certain idea, opinion, or action. Of course, in this case it requires the use of strong arguments, to influence the target's thinking or behavior. The goal is to get others to agree or act in accordance with our wishes. In a persuasive approach, we can use a persuasive communication approach model called *Logical argument (logos)*. This persuasive approach is the delivery of messages through invitations using arguments from the data that has been found. Meanwhile, the informative approach emphasizes the delivery of accurate, relevant, and useful information to others. It involves sharing data, facts, statistics, or other knowledge to provide a better understanding of an issue, concept, or situation. This approach does not necessarily seek to convince, but rather focuses on providing others with a better understanding. Experimental research has shown that strong arguments are more persuasive than weak arguments, that strong messages often have more positive consequences for the recipient. ²⁹

The form of approach that researchers took was to hold meetings with village stakeholders. The activity took the form of socialization with the aim of providing knowledge and understanding related to the village TPPS. During the meeting, the researcher explained that the TPPS is tasked with coordinating, synergizing and evaluating the implementation of efforts to accelerate stunting reduction in the village, and that there is also a national action plan matrix, one of which contains targets that must be achieved and this can be known without having to wait for data information from other parties. For example, the target coverage of catinine who have a health check 3 months before marriage is 100%. The TPPS must then collect and process catin data to ensure that the target is achieved. If the target is not achieved, an evaluation will be conducted as soon as possible to take corrective or improvement actions. In addition, if so far the head of the PKK driving team, the village secretary does not seem to have the authority to accelerate efforts to reduce stunting, then through the TPPS this authority is given.

This is different from the duties and functions of the KPM and TPK. Regarding the limited funds, the researcher suggested that the principle of TPPS membership is voluntary. This is the same as the recruitment of posyandu cadres when it was first established. As for the issue of limited human resources, the researcher explained that if you look at the composition of the TPPS membership, only a few new people need to be recruited.

This is because the director of the TPPS is the village head, the chairperson is the head of the PKK mobilization team, the vice chairperson is the village secretary, and the secretary is a family planning cadre. In addition, the coordinators are midwives/other personnel and KPM. Thus, only members will be recruited to fill the positions of members in the field of the family assistance team and the field of data management. Regarding the accumulation of work, the researcher explained that they were used to doing this work. Especially when it comes to data related to targets such as in the RAN PASTI matrix that is already available to them.

CONCLUSIONS

The barriers to the formation of the village TPPS were no technical socialization of the TPPS formation from the authorities, the perception that the village had already formed an activity team that was also working to reduce stunting, limited funds to provide honorarium/incentives for team members, and limited human resources. To overcome these obstacles, a persuasive and informative approach was taken to the village government.

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